

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING STATISTICAL MATERIALS IN TEACHING GEOGRAPHY**Naghiyeva Irada Isa gizi***Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University**Head teacher**Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogy, Honored Teacher*<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-7022-1243>**Abstract**

The article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of using statistical materials in geography teaching. The scientific importance of collecting, systematizing, analyzing, and presenting statistical data in graphical and cartographic forms in geographical research and the educational process is substantiated. The quantitative and qualitative components of statistical analysis, indexing methods, and the application of individual and aggregate indices within the school geography curriculum are analyzed. The role of mathematical statistics in studying physical-geographical and socio-economic processes is highlighted. The impact of statistical graphs, diagrams, and thematic maps on the development of students' spatial thinking and analytical skills is explained. The study concludes that the systematic application of statistical methods in geography teaching enhances the scientific understanding of geographical processes and increases the overall effectiveness of the educational process.

Keywords: geography teaching, statistical materials, mathematical statistics, statistical analysis, indexing methods, graphical techniques, thematic maps, analytical thinking

Introduction

In conducting geographical research, the logical analysis of statistical materials is of great importance in determining quantitative and qualitative parameters. Each analyzed geographical scientific object is preceded by the logical probability of its statistical indicators. The issue is measured by the fact that geographical research is based on the analysis of quantitative and qualitative general statistical regularities. The geographical character or distinctive features of the studied units and objects is an important area of statistical research. The character of statistical research is determined depending on the content and the source of ideas of the topic. The importance of statistical analysis in studying the research areas of geographical science is that scientific research of certain statistical materials that ensure the qualitatively sustainable development of any units is brought to the fore. The character or distinctive features of the geography of the analyzed units and objects are carried out with the results of research topics based on the realities of analytical statistical logic having a more complete content.[1]

The functional structure of analytical statistical analysis is divided into two important classifications: quantitative and qualitative. Within the framework of the classification of quantitative expression, the level indicators of the variants expressed in numbers in accordance with the research (for example, analysis of temperature changes in altitudinal zones in numbers, chronology of the production structure, etc.) are clarified. Quality, on the other hand, is determined by the effectiveness of statistical indicators of a geographical object in accordance with the nature of the research, reflecting the dynamics affecting its territorial organization. The logical basis of geographical scientific creativity is considered to be the formation and dialectics of the territorial production structural system. Analytical statistical analysis, on the other hand, gives a kind of "energy" to the dynamics of

quantitative and qualitative relations between structural areas.

In the transformation of geographical scientific research into a new content, the areas of application of mathematical statistics have more effective results. In particular, in the complex study of physical geographical, cartographic, geographical economic analyses, etc., mathematical statistical scientific sources are used. The role and position of the English scientific school in the formation of mathematical statistical science is of theoretical interest. Karl Pearson published more than 400 scientific works on the problems of mathematical statistics. It is more important that his scientific and methodological research on the theoretical foundations of correlation, algorithmic decision-making, etc. is widely used in modern times.

R. Piriyev's services in conducting mathematical statistical analyses in Azerbaijani geography are commendable. The main direction of the scientist's scientific research covers the system of methods used in the study and application of relief morphometry. For the first time in this direction, a methodology for compiling a number of medium-scale relief maps was developed using mathematical statistics. There is an absolute advantage of statistical graphic analyses in the effect of the ideas put forward against the background of qualitative research in geography. These methods create opportunities for substantiating geographical phenomena and research objects. The advantage of the practice of statistical graphics is the emphasis on the technique of their systematic, cartographic, etc. construction.[5]

It is essential for every researcher to understand the connection between geographic statistical graphs and the topic and the technique of constructing analytical graphs related to the problem.

In general, statistical graphs are divided into:

- type of graph (nature of the expressed quantity, content);

- area of the graph (spaces where geometric symbols are located);
- scale of the graph (graphic scale system of numerical quantities).

Depending on the method of construction, form and the nature of the problems being analyzed, two

main types of graphics are used: diagrams and statistical maps. In diagrams, statistical information is expressed primarily by linear and geometric figures and symbolic signs. In statistical maps, the contours of geographical objects are indicated by conventional signs, quantities, etc. (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Income changes in the PRC and the Russian Federation.

Linear graphs are expressed in the form of functions of "space-time" changes in geographical processes. In such diagrams, the circle is preferred to denote the level of the studied process, and the radius is the period. A rectangular coordinate system is mainly used to construct linear graphs. The values of the abscissa axis are taken as the basis. Statistical indices are widely used in geographical research. Indices are a special relative quantity. Through them, the functions of changes in geographical phenomena in time and space are determined. The results obtained by such methods are considered acceptable for determining the nature of the dynamics of the analyzed phenomena, their structure and dialectical relationships.[4]

The methodology of analysis of geographical-statistical research uses individual and aggregate indices. An individual index is calculated only when determining the level of change of a geographical research process over two or more "space-time" intersecting periods. If quantitative information about the studied geographical object is provided for several years or several periods, then it can be calculated according to chain and base indices.

The chain volume index is calculated based on data provided for four periods. When studying economic and social phenomena, it is often preferred to calculate final indices. In addition, aggregate indices and weighted average indices are also used to study complex phenomena that cannot be compared with each other. Example. Let's calculate the individual volume and price index of a product (statistical indicators are symbolic). A) base index by product volume: suppose that factory A produced 1.2 liters of product in January and 1.1 liters of product in February. Then $1.1: 1.2 = 0.916$. B) base index by product price: suppose that factory A produced 1.2 liters of product in January at 45 manats, and in February at 1.1 liter. the price was 43 manats. Then $43: 45 = 0.955$

The analysis shows that the convergence of the index to unity indicates a high quality parameter. This approach is used in the analysis of issues such as quantitative and qualitative justification in geographical scientific research. As a rule, the indexing method provides an opportunity to study and analyze processes and phenomena in all areas of geographical science. When studying the indexing method of analysis, it is also necessary to pay attention to the explanation of differentiation issues as a continuation of this method. The differentiation of absolute or relative quantitative changes based on mathematical approaches is one of the analytical statistical analyses widely used in the qualitative study of the mutual relations of individual geographical factors. The use of mathematical and statistical methods is considered an important option for the sustainable development of the practice of geographical and economic analysis. Its application increases the usefulness of the analysis of the activities of territorial and production structures. As a result, economic factors are revealed, and forms of functional dependence between geographical complexes of result indicators are determined.[7]

During geographical research, statistics solves the following scientific problems:

1. Collection of statistical data consists of sources from which statistical data can be taken ready-made from various publications (statistical collections, reference books, bulletins, newspapers, magazines, maps, atlases) and collected during specially organized statistical observations, or a targeted survey. Obtaining the necessary initial data is not only the initial task, but also the most difficult and important operation of each study. For this reason, serious attention is paid to statistical observation.

2. Since the obtained quantitative data is processed and systematized through statistical summarization and grouping, the collected data can be processed and used more widely in geographical research.

3. Analysis and interpretation of data is their comparison, as well as comparison with each other, calculation of the necessary statistical indicators with initial values, obtaining conclusions and determining the relevant characteristics and development patterns of the objects and phenomena under consideration.

4. It is the presentation of statistical data in text, tables, graphs or cartographic forms, thus making it convenient for storage and visual perception by students for further use.[6]

The role of statistics in solving these problems creates opportunities for the formation of an information base of a geography in which quantitative data plays an important role. Statistical indicators include absolute and relative values, as well as various coefficients.

Absolute values are informative and indicate the size of geographical phenomena. For example, Russia has the largest territory in the world - more than 17 million km², which is almost twice the area of countries such as China or the United States. It is also one of the largest countries in terms of population. As of January 1, 2009, 141.9 million people lived in Russia.[2]

Relative values represent the results of comparing statistical indicators with each other. They allow us to detect certain regular changes in geographical phenomena, such as population density. Coefficients are indicators that reflect the characteristic features of individual phenomena, for example, the coefficient of specialization or the coefficient of natural population growth, etc.

To learn how to work with statistical tables, we must first understand how they are organized. A statistical table is a system of vertical and horizontal graphs, provided with headings and filled with numerical data in a certain order. It contains statistical information necessary to characterize the geographical phenomenon under study and its components.

When we read any statistical table, we see that it begins with a general title.

Statistical materials can be presented not only in statistical tables, but also in visual form: in diagrams, graphs, maps and schematic maps, etc.[3]

It is clear that statistical data quickly becomes outdated and requires constant updating. Online educational resources are a great help in this.

Relevance of the article.In the modern educational system, strengthening scientifically based approaches and forming analytical thinking skills in students is considered one of the priority directions. Since geography studies the spatial distribution, interrelations and dynamics of natural and socio-economic processes, analysis based on statistical data is an integral part of the content of this subject. In this regard, the issue of purposeful and systematic use of statistical materials in geography teaching acts as an urgent scientific and methodological problem.

In the context of globalization, socio-economic indicators of the countries of the world, demographic processes, urbanization, climate change and other geographical phenomena are characterized by statistical indicators. The ability of students to correctly read, analyze, compare and draw conclusions from this

information directly affects the formation of their scientific worldview. However, the use of statistical materials in teaching practice is often formal in nature and a systematic approach is needed from a methodological point of view.

Visualizing data through statistical graphs, diagrams, tables, and thematic maps allows for a deeper understanding of geographic objects and processes. This in turn develops spatial thinking, comparative analysis, and generalization skills in students.

Thus, investigating the theoretical and methodological foundations of using statistical materials in teaching geography, and determining ways to systematically apply them in the teaching process, is a relevant and practically important research direction in terms of modern educational requirements.

Scientific novelty of the article.The scientific novelty of the article is related to the substantiation of a systematic and complex methodological model of using statistical materials in teaching geography. Within the framework of the study, the quantitative and qualitative components of statistical analysis were integrated with the content of geography lessons based on a unified pedagogical approach.

For the first time, the application of statistical materials - tables, diagrams, graphs, thematic maps and indexes - in the teaching process has been justified not only as a means of presenting information, but also as a functional didactic mechanism serving to form students' analytical and spatial thinking. The possibilities of applying statistical indexing, comparative analysis and interpretation of dynamic indicators in the mastering of geography topics have been systematized from a scientific and methodological point of view.

In addition, the pedagogical effectiveness of using mathematical statistical methods in teaching physical-geographical and socio-economic processes has been substantiated, and the connection between the visualization of statistical data and a clearer understanding of spatial patterns has been identified.

As a result of the research, it has been proven that the purposeful application of statistical materials in teaching is an innovative methodological approach that serves the scientific mastery of the subject of geography and the development of students' research-oriented thinking skills.

Practical significance of the article.The practical importance of using statistical materials in teaching geography is manifested, first of all, in ensuring the completeness of scientific results through a logical analysis of the quantitative and qualitative parameters of the studied geographical objects and phenomena. This methodology serves to reveal economic factors and determine functional dependencies between geographical complexes, giving a kind of "energy" to the dynamic relations between territorial-production structures.

The practical significance of the article is that the scientific-methodological approaches presented here provide specific application mechanisms for the effective use of statistical materials in teaching geography. The methodological recommendations on

the collection, grouping, analysis and presentation of statistical data in graphic and cartographic form allow teachers to build the teaching process on a more systematic and analytical basis.

The methods of indexing, comparative analysis, and visualization substantiated in the study create practical conditions for the development of spatial thinking, analytical thinking, and statistical literacy in students. These approaches allow for effective results, especially in the mastery of socio-economic and physical-geographical topics.

Thus, statistics, in addition to forming the information base of geography, allows us to scientifically substantiate the real geographical picture (for example, population density or natural growth) through absolute and relative indicators.

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